

Exploring Students' Self-Potential as a Motivation for Entrepreneurship

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Abstract:- Introduction/Main Objectives: Since 1998 one of the programmes that has been developed is the Student Creativity Programme (PKM) Entrepreneurship and Co-op (Cooperative Education Program), with the aim of forming entrepreneurs through higher education. **Background Problems:** In order for entrepreneurship programmes to run continuously in universities and have a systematically planned and progressive management system, each university must continue to increase the role of special institutions for the development of entrepreneurship centres and national productivity. **Novelty:** This institution is expected to systematically change and or improve the quality of the existing education or learning system so that students not only have knowledge and expertise in their knowledge, but are also able to utilise and process their knowledge to increase the value of resources available in the community for their own welfare and the welfare of the community and nation. **Research Methods:** The descriptive analysis method is carried out by describing the facts which are then followed by analysis, this qualitative descriptive approach is used by the author to analyse in order to obtain the results to be achieved. **Finding/Results:** Recognising students' entrepreneurial potential can be assessed from six aspects, namely: personality, self-discipline, creativity, drive/desire, risk-taking courage, and self-confidence. Whether or not recognising the potential in students can give an idea of how far a person feels he needs to improve himself and learn to be better. **Conclusion:** Knowing oneself means gaining knowledge about the totality of the right self, namely realising the advantages / advantages possessed and the shortcomings / weaknesses that exist in oneself which will later become a source of success in entrepreneurship.

Keywords:- *Self Potential, Motivation, Entrepreneurship,*

I. INTRODUCTION

The Central Statistics Agency (BPS) stated that the unemployment rate in Indonesia in August 2022 reached 8.42 million people, resulting in an open unemployment rate (TPT) of 5.86%. Every year this unemployment remains a problem that must be resolved. The limited absorption of university graduates in the government sector has caused attention to turn

to opportunities to work in the private sector, but the severity of the requirements set sometimes makes opportunities to work in the private sector also increasingly limited. The only opportunity that is still very large is to work by starting an independent business in the form of entrepreneurship both off line and on line.

In an effort to foster an entrepreneurial spirit and increase entrepreneurial activity so that university graduates become job creators, the Ministry of Education and Culture has developed various policies and programmes. Since 1998 one of the programmes that has been developed is the Student Creativity Programme (PKM) Entrepreneurship and Co-op (Cooperative Education Program), with the aim of forming entrepreneurs through higher education.

Starting in 2003, the Co-op programme was developed, which provides integrated work-learning opportunities in the Student Activity Unit (UKM). In order for entrepreneurship programmes to run continuously in higher education and have a systematically planned and progressive management system, each university must continue to increase the role of special institutions for the development of entrepreneurship centres and national productivity. This institution is expected to systematically change and or improve the quality of the existing education or learning system so that students not only have knowledge and expertise in their knowledge, but are also able to utilise and process their knowledge to increase the value of resources available in society for their own welfare and the welfare of society and the nation.

In order to develop ourselves as potential entrepreneurs, we need to recognise who we really are and how others assess us (Suryana, 2011). To assess ourselves, the initial process is that we must know the weaknesses that exist in us and improve them, the second is to recognise what potential is contained in us which we then turn into a competency wrapped in a good attitude, then we can achieve what we want (success). Many people interpret success in material terms. However, the real success is our ability to recognise the potential within ourselves and maximise it into a competence, and that competence is used to achieve something better. If the potential within us is to become an entrepreneur then we must maximise our potential.

Entrepreneurial motivation must be possessed by individuals who have the desire to become successful entrepreneurs, because having high entrepreneurial motivation can form a mindset of independence and freedom personally and financially. Entrepreneurial motivation is a driving factor in generating interest in entrepreneurship. Motivation can come from internal and external individuals. Entrepreneurial motivation can be trained, learned and developed because entrepreneurial motivation is not brought since a person is born. The success of an entrepreneur is one of them has a strong motivation in achieving its goals. Along with the need for motivation based on the willingness and desire of individuals to achieve a goal, we should not forget how important mental attitude coaching. Mental attitude is the behaviour that arises from a person's soul as a situation that affects him. For entrepreneurs to be able to run their business, they must make careful calculations, meaning that an entrepreneur must be ready to make decisions whatever happens. To be able to compete in the business world, qualified human resources are needed. To explore one's potential, a strong mental attitude is needed, self-potential is usually obtained from one's knowledge and personal experience. Thus, the resources can be developed and explored in accordance with the knowledge and experience gained by each individual. knowledge of entrepreneurial motivation, business, financial management, marketing, and others through entrepreneurship courses. And the events organised by the campus regarding entrepreneurship include seminars, trainings and rombong parties where students are trained in entrepreneurship.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Some theoretical foundations that may be relevant to the exploration of students' self-potential as a motivation for entrepreneurship. You may combine these theories according to your research focus:

A. Motivation Theories:

- Hierarchy of Needs Theory (Maslow): According to Maslow, basic human needs such as security, social relationships, esteem, and self-actualisation can be motivational drivers to achieve maximum potential. In this context, the exploration of students' self-potential can be linked to efforts to achieve self-actualisation through entrepreneurship.
- Self-Determination Theory (Deci and Ryan): This theory suggests that human motivation can stem from basic needs for autonomy, relatedness, and competence. Motivating students to explore their potential can be key to fulfilling these needs and encouraging intrinsic motivation.

B. Career Development Theory:

- Super's Career Development Theory: Donald Super proposes that career development is a lifelong process, and individuals actively seek to learn about themselves and the world of work. Exploring students' potential can be linked to the exploration stage of career development.
- Integrative Life Planning Theory (Savickas): Savickas emphasises the importance of designing a meaningful life and career by understanding oneself. Exploration of self-potential can be an integral part of holistic life and career planning.

C. Entrepreneurship Theory:

- Social Entrepreneurship Theory (Dees): Focuses on creating social and environmental value through business ventures. Encouraging students to explore their potential can involve entrepreneurial thinking that includes social and environmental aspects.
- Entrepreneurial Efficacy Theory (Bandura): This theory highlights the role of an individual's self-belief in their ability to succeed in an entrepreneurial context. Exploring one's potential can increase students' entrepreneurial efficacy.

D. Educational Theory:

- Constructivism Theory (Piaget and Vygotsky): Emphasises the active role of students in constructing their own knowledge. In this context, exploring self-potential can be considered as part of the construction of knowledge about self and entrepreneurship.
- Experiential Learning Theory (Kolb): Kolb suggests that learning is more effective when it involves a cycle of reflective experiences. Exploring students' self-potential can be a reflective learning experience, promoting self-understanding and entrepreneurial ability.

As further research, you can combine and relate these theories according to your research framework and focus. Be sure to consider the context and purpose of your research in formulating the most appropriate theoretical foundation.

III. METHOD, DATA, AND ANALYSIS

The descriptive analysis method is carried out by describing the facts which are then followed by analysis, this qualitative descriptive approach is used by the author to analyse in order to obtain the results to be achieved. Not merely describing, but also providing sufficient understanding and explanation. activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and continuously until completion which is described in four steps. The four steps are (data

collection), data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing/verification. Conclusion drawing or verification is the third step in the data analysis process. After the data is analysed continuously at the time of data collection during the process and after the field, then the process of drawing conclusions or verification of the results is carried out in accordance with the data that researchers collect from field findings. Conclusions that were initially very tentative, vague and doubtful, will become more grounded. This process is carried out starting from drawing conclusions with continuous verification to check back in the field, there may be parts that are added or omitted so that the final conclusions obtained after being assessed and checked again do not change.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

❖ Discussion

A. Definition of self-potential

Many people define success in material terms. But real success is our ability to recognise the potential within ourselves and maximise it into competence, and that competence is used to achieve something better. If the potential within us is to become an entrepreneur then we must maximise our potential. As a first step, students need to recognise the behaviours, attitudes and value systems that make up the whole personality. In addition to personality, abilities need to be recognised.

Capabilities are determined primarily by knowledge and skills. The knowledge that students should have is essentially to know themselves, the environment, the field of business they are entering, know what to do, and be familiar with the processes and systems handled, what is achieved, how to achieve it, and the risks, and how to overcome these risks. planning in other words, a student needs to have sufficient knowledge to be able to direct himself, obtain business opportunities, develop business concepts, create, enter the market, operate (in an organisation / alone), and thus enjoy added value and develop himself.

➤ Types of Self-Potential

- conceptual skills in organising strategies and calculating risks;
- have leadership and management skills
- have technical skills in the business field
- have communication and interaction skills, and have creative skills to create added value.

Skills are not only to be known, but also require adequate training to develop and sharpen the skills we have. To do entrepreneurship, we need to conduct an assessment of ourselves and from outside ourselves, which will determine the success and failure of our business. According to Suryana (2011), the assessment of entrepreneurial potential can be seen from six aspects, namely aspects of personality, self-discipline, creativity, drive/desire, courage to face risks, and

self-confidence. Personality, is the overall inherited or acquired psychological quality that is unique to a person that makes him unique. With a person's personality he can attract other people, people sympathise with him, people are interested in his conversation, people are amazed by him. Entrepreneurs who have this kind of personality are often successful in running their business. Self-discipline, is the accuracy of the entrepreneur's commitment to his duties and work. The accuracy in question is comprehensive, namely accuracy to time, quality of work, work systems and so on. Accuracy to time can be fostered in a person by trying to complete the work in accordance with the planned time. Creativity, is the ability to make new combinations or see new relationships between elements, data, variables that already exist. Encouragement / Desire for entrepreneurship can come from friends, family environment, friends where they can discuss entrepreneurial ideas, problems faced and ways to solve problems. The courage to face the risk exists when the time to come (future) is unknown (unknown). So, in other words, risk exists when there is uncertainty. Self-confidence, a person with high self-confidence is a person who is physically and mentally mature. This kind of person is an independent person. The characteristics of a person's maturity are that he does not depend on others, he has a high sense of responsibility, is objective and critical.

B. Entrepreneurial Interest

One way to foster entrepreneurship is by knowing one's own interest and potential in entrepreneurship. Potential is the basic ability a person has that is very likely to be developed by ourselves. In order to develop ourselves as potential entrepreneurs, we need to recognise who we really are and how others assess us (Suryana, 2011). To assess ourselves, the initial process is that we must know the weaknesses that exist in us and improve them, the second is to recognise what potential is contained in us which we then turn into a competency wrapped in a good attitude, then we can achieve what we want (success). Many people interpret success in material terms. However, the real success is our ability to recognise the potential within ourselves and maximise it into a competence, and that competence is used to achieve something better. If the potential within us is to become an entrepreneur then we must maximise our potential.

Interest is a source of motivation that drives one to do what one wants to do when one is free to choose. When someone considers that something will be useful, an interest will be formed which will then bring satisfaction from it. When satisfaction decreases, interest will also decrease so that interest is not permanent, but rather temporary or changeable. Entrepreneurship is someone who is able to create jobs with creativity and is able to manage risks and then utilise these risks into business opportunities. According to Fanny Paramitasari (2016), it is someone who has a sense of interest in something that is creative, innovative and able to create business opportunities and manage risks with the output of goods or services. Entrepreneurial interest is not only owned

just like that, but also needs to be explored more. Because a strong interest can create a successful entrepreneur.

➤ *Aspects of interest in a person, namely:*

- Encouragement from within to fulfil personal needs as a driving source to do something.
- The need to relate to his social environment which will determine the position of the individual in his environment.
- Individual feelings towards the work he does.

Little or no by recognising the potential that exists in students can provide an overview of how far a person feels he needs to improve himself and learn to be better. Knowing yourself means gaining knowledge about the totality of the right self, namely realising the advantages / advantages possessed and the shortcomings / weaknesses that exist in oneself which will later become a source of success in entrepreneurship. There are ten things that a successful entrepreneur must have and always remember, namely: (1) Find your purpose and Dream all the time, which is success in a journey not a destination; (2) Neverending Innovation, which is non-stop innovation; (3) Learn-Cchange and Grow: Always learn, learn, and learn; (4) Accumulate your assets: the ultimate goal of entrepreneurship is to achieve financial success; (5) Use Leverage concept to build your business: a smart entrepreneur must be able to use other people's energy and time to achieve their goals; (6) Develop your people: able to use other people's energy and time to achieve their goals; (7) Systemise your business: able to build an effective and efficient business system; (8) Build network and alliance: able to create a strong network both in terms of business opportunities, capital, and access to government; (9) Be Smart investor: one of the strengths of smart and successful entrepreneurs is the ability to manage their asset portopolio so that it is always growing and increasing; (10) The Power of Giving: Give and be Grateful: a true entrepreneur's habit is to give and be grateful.

C. Motivation

Understanding Motivation according to Hamalik (1992: 173) defines Motivation is energy that changes in a person with a reaction and feeling to achieve a certain goal. Mc Donald (Oemar Hamalik, 2002: 174) says motivation is an energy that changes from within a person which results in a reaction and affective to achieve goals. G.R Terry says that motivation is an impulse that arises in a person and can cause an action. Motivation is closely related to the willingness to do something for individual desires, needs and drives. If the goal has been achieved, someone will feel satisfaction.

According to Sadirman (2005: 89) motivation can be divided into two, namely:

- Intrinsic motivation, is motivation that arises from within a person

- Extrinsic motivation, is motivation that arises from the environment or from outside a person.

From the understanding and definition of motivation of the experts above, it can be concluded that motivation is an impetus that can move someone to do something he does to achieve certain goals. Elliot et al., (2000); Sue Howard, (1999) said that self and environment can generate and develop motivation in each individual.

According to Abu Ahmadi (Yuyus Suryana and Kartib Bayu, 2013: 98) motivation is a determining factor in a person in achieving his goals. Because psychological motivation is the basis of the elements of a person's behaviour. Motivation exists because of a desire, a strong drive from within. Meanwhile, motives arise because of a need that must be fulfilled.

According to Paramitasari (2016) Entrepreneurial motivation is an impulse that arises within the individual and makes decisions to achieve goals in the field of entrepreneurship. When someone feels that what he wants must be achieved that's where the drive from within appears. In addition, motivation can be interpreted as an internal and external drive in a person characterised by desires and interests; drives and needs; hopes and ideals; appreciation and respect. Motivation does not only arise from within a person but also from the surrounding environment (Uno, 2007).

Entrepreneurial motivation can be trained, learnt and developed because entrepreneurial motivation is not carried since a person is born. Therefore, entrepreneurial motivation is a drive within a person that is able to influence entrepreneurial interest based on what he trains and learns. A person can be motivated as an entrepreneur because there are many things he can get by becoming an entrepreneur. For example, in terms of profit, freedom, ideals and independence. A person with entrepreneurship will have the opportunity to earn a large income and entrepreneurship is also able to create jobs for others, besides that, entrepreneurship can also contribute to the state through taxes generated.

D. Entrepreneurship

There are different definitions of Entrepreneurship according to several experts, namely:

John J. Kao (1993) defines Entrepreneurship as an attempt to create value through the recognition of business opportunities, appropriate risk-taking management, and through communication and management skills to mobilise people, money, and raw materials or other resources needed to produce projects to be carried out properly.

According to Robert D. Hisrich (2005) Entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of creating additional wealth. Wealth is created by individuals who dare to take major risks on

reasonable terms, time, and or career commitments or the provision of value for various goods and services.

Robert D. Hisrich (2005) more fully defines entrepreneurship based on three approaches, namely the economist, psychologist, and businessman approaches. The explanation is as follows:

- Economist Approach. Entrepreneurship is a person who brings resources, energy, materials, and other assets into a combination that makes their value higher than before, and also someone who introduces change, innovation / renewal, and a new order / order or world order.
- Psychological Approach. Entrepreneurship is really a person who is characteristically driven by certain forces, activities to produce or achieve something, on experiments, on improvements, or perhaps on the authority to find other solutions.
- The businessman's approach. Entrepreneurship is a businessman who appears as a threat, an aggressive competitor, whereas in other businesses fellow entrepreneurs may be an ally / partner, a source of supply, a customer, or someone who creates wealth for others, also finds more ways to utilise resources, reduce waste, and generate new jobs for others who are happy to run it.

According to the Presidential instruction NO.4 Year 1995: "Entrepreneurship is the spirit, attitude, behaviour, and ability of a person in handling business and or activities that lead to efforts to seek, create, apply new ways of working, technology, and products in improving efficiency in order to provide better service and or obtain greater profits".

Entrepreneurship is our ability to recognise the potential within ourselves and maximise it into a competence, and that competence is used to achieve something better. If the potential within us is to become an entrepreneur then we must maximise our potential. As a first step, entrepreneurial students need to recognise the behaviours, attitudes and value systems that make up the whole personality.

In addition to personality, personal capabilities need to be recognised. Capabilities are determined primarily by knowledge and skills. The knowledge that entrepreneurial students should have is essentially knowing themselves, the environment, the field of business they are entering, knowing what to do, and being familiar with the processes and systems handled, what is achieved, how to achieve it, and the risks, and how to overcome these risks. In other words, an entrepreneurial student needs to have sufficient knowledge to be able to direct himself, obtain business opportunities, develop business concepts, make plans, enter the market, operate (in organisations / alone), and thus enjoy added value and develop himself.

It can be concluded that entrepreneurship is matters and efforts related to the creation of activities or businesses or business activities on the basis of their own will and

establishing a business or business with their own willingness and ability. Entrepreneurs are people who have entrepreneurial traits and generally have the courage to take risks, especially in handling their business or company based on their own abilities or willingness.

V. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Entrepreneurship is matters and efforts related to the creation of activities or businesses or business activities on the basis of their own will and establishing a business or business with their own willingness and ability. Entrepreneurs are people who have entrepreneurial traits and generally have the courage to take risks, especially in handling their business or company based on their own abilities or willingness.

The knowledge that entrepreneurs should have is the essence of knowing themselves, the environment, the business field they enter, knowing what to do, and knowing the processes and systems handled, what is achieved, how to achieve it, and risks, and how to overcome these risks. In other words, an entrepreneur needs to have sufficient knowledge and skills to be able to direct himself, obtain business opportunities, develop business concepts, make plans, enter the market and operate within (his own organisation). Skills are not only to be known, but adequate training is also needed to develop and sharpen the skills we have. To do entrepreneurship, we need to make judgements about ourselves and from outside ourselves, which will determine the success and failure of our business.

One way to foster entrepreneurship is to recognise one's own interest and potential in entrepreneurship. Potential is the basic ability a person has that is very likely to be developed by ourselves. Interest is a source of motivation that drives one to do what one wants to do when one is free to choose. When someone assesses that something will be useful, an interest will be formed which will then bring satisfaction from this. When satisfaction decreases, interest will also decrease so that interest is not permanent, but rather temporary or changeable.

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